

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

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Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

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ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14576256>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14681685>

Integral Yoga of Sri Aurobindo

Remya.S¹

Aurobindo Ghosh was born on the fifteenth of August 1872 at Konagar, west Bengal. Aurobindo was a brilliant student who excelled in classics, literature and History. The basic aim of Sri Aurobindo's philosophy is "to solve the fundamental problems of human life" (Purani 207). According to him life is a dynamic energy. It is the manifestation of the consciousness - force of saccidananda. His thought is highly influenced by the Philosophy of the Bhagavadgita. He also studied the ancient Indian Philosophies including the darsanas - particularly those of Advaita Vedanta and Yoga. According to him. "Yoga means union with the Divine, a union either transcendental (above the Universe) or cosmic (Universal) or individual, or as in our yoga, all three together" (Aurobindo 16) It was the reason for it is called integral.

Yoga helps and expedites the process of ascent, which is nothing but a process of widening, heightening and integration. Yoga helps all these aspects of evolution and therefore it is integral. Integral yoga was also called as purna yoga. The integral method of the synthesis of yoga produces integral results. There is first an integral realisation of Divine Being, and there is also an integral liberation, mukti, not only Sayujya mukti in which the individual being attains unbroken contact in all its parts with the Divine, not only Salokya mukti by which the whole conscious existence dwells in the state of sachidhananda, but also sadharmya mukti, in which the divine nature is acquired by the transformation of the lower being.

Sri Aurobindo points out that the purely intellectual and sentimental religion of humanity is no sufficient to bring about the needed great change in human Psychology. When the ego attains

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Liberty, it arrives first at strife and then at an attempt to ignore the variations of nature, and it constructs an artificial and machine-made Society, when the ego asserts fraternity, it speaks of something contrary to its nature, all that ego knows is association for the pursuit of common egoistic ends and the most that it can arrive at is a closer organisation for the equal distribution of labour, production, consumption and enjoyment. The gospel of the idea of humanism is to be fulfilled, we have to realise that brother hood is the real key and that the brotherhood exists only in the soul and by the Soul, and also he concludes that the religion of humanity must be a spiritual religion of humanity, not an institutional religion, not an intellectual religion, not a sentimental religion.

Integral yoga, thus aims at the Divine transformation of the whole of the embodied existence and also includes sarvamukti or the collective liberation of the mankind

Reality - Saccidananda

The nature of the reality, it is essential to consider the levels or the cords of being as they have been conceived by Sri. Aurobindo. Creation is the expression in terms of manifoldness. He also describes reality as saccidananda, it is nothing but a common name for the triune principle of Existence, consciousness-force and Bliss. The highest experience of this reality in the universe shows it to be not only a conscious Existence, But a Supreme Intelligence and force and a self-existent bliss.

According to him the absolute is not only sat and cit it is also called ananda. "Brahman is infinite bliss or the infinite delight of the creative play of the force" (3). He was aware that Brahman conceived as Existent and as conscious force may be conceived as a complete notion; so that there may not remain any need for the Supreme reality. He also feels that Delight can be the only reason for creation. He describes creation as the ecstatic dance of Siva, and as such the purpose of creation can be nothing else but the joy of the dancing. This joy or bliss is also as Universal and ineffable as pure Existent or consciousness - force. According to Sri. Aurobindo the self-delight or Bliss of saccidananda is limitless. It is capable of infinite variety; it is expressed in every aspect of existence and conscious activities.

The four Theories of Existence

Sri. Aurobindo comes to discover four theories of existence. They are,

- i. The Supercosmic
- ii. The cosmic or Terrestrial
- iii. The supra-terrestrial or the other - worldly
- iv. Integral or the Synthetic.

i. The Super cosmic Theory

The Super cosmic Theory, the Absolute alone is real. Its monistic character is so clear that in such a theory the reality of everything else, even of man tends to suffer. In this theory even human existence does not have any real meaning; it is conceived as a mistake of the soul or a delirium of the will to live or as an error or ignorance which somehow over casts the Absolute reality. He also places Advaita Vedanta under this Super cosmic theory. Sri. Aurobindo criticises this theory on the ground that it reduces world to the status of an illusion or a dream or an image. He also criticises this theory on the ground that it is extremely one sided and partial.

ii. The Cosmic or the Terrestrial Theory

The cosmic theory is the exact opposite of the Super-cosmic. It considers cosmic existence as real. It goes further and accepts the cosmic reality as the only reality. The defect of this theory was it fails to notice the possibility of the beyond. It overlooks the fact that every individual is capable of certain nobility of being of going beyond the terrestrial.

iii. The Supra terrestrial theory

This theory believes both in the reality of the world as well as in the reality of something higher. It tries to reconcile the Supra-cosmic and the cosmic - terrestrial views because it admits the reality of both the 'material cosmos' and 'the transcendent world'. This theory also believes that the earth is a place for a temporary stay sojourn of the soul, but it also believes that behind the mortality of the bodily life of man there is the soul's immortality. In a sense theistic philosophies and religion would fall under this category. It also believes that the possibility of a higher world in which soul in its immortality can enter.

iv. Integral or the Synthetic

Sri Aurobindo developed his own metaphysical theory; it is truly synthetic or integral. He believes that for a really synthetic theory. The reality both of the cosmos and the higher realm has to

be maintained. Such a theory is really synthetic and integral because it synthesises both the Supra-cosmic and Cosmic-terrestrial theories in an obviously more harmonious manner than the Supra-terrestrial theory.

Sri. Aurobindo Claims that his yoga is integral or synthetic, because firstly, it comprehends all forms of yoga and secondly, it emphasises such aspects of yoga - discipline that are missed by other forms of yoga. Knowledge and Devotion, for example, are not opposed to each other and yet Jnanamarga and Bhakti Yoga assert and lay emphasis on their own ways. Sri. Aurobindo feels that what is needed is an all-round and total development. The growth of knowledge alone or the perfection and control of only the body, or the way of intense devotion will not bring about the change. What is needed is a total transformation of all aspects of being the mental, the vital and the physical. Therefore, only that process can be purnayoga which will aim at the complete transformation of every aspect of being. This is the aim of Sri. Aurobindo's yoga and therefore it is called integral.

As a modern Indian philosopher, Aurobindo has given to the world a very comprehensive philosophical system and integral sociology which points to mankind the true way of attaining "Integral living" that is the highest form of terrestrial life in general Aurobindo's Integral Philosophy intended for all time and all peoples, and its teachings are actually applicable at any time and in any place.

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Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,